

PROGNOSTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF *HELICOBACTER PYLORI* PRESENCE IN GASTRIC ADENOCARCINOMAS

Keywords

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ABSTRACT

Gastric adenocarcinoma remains a major global health burden, with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) recognized as its most significant risk factor. While the bacterium's role in carcinogenesis is well established, its prognostic impact after cancer development remains unclear. This retrospective study included 69 patients diagnosed with gastric adenocarcinoma at Sivas Cumhuriyet University between January 2023 and December 2024. Demographic, clinical, and pathological features were retrieved from hospital records. Histopathological evaluation included tumor localization, grade, subtype, and presence of intestinal metaplasia. *H. pylori* status was assessed by histochemical Giemsa staining. Overall survival (OS) was calculated and compared between *H. pylori*-positive and -negative groups. The cohort comprised 49 males (71.0%) and 20 females (29.0%), with a median follow-up of 36 months. Intestinal-type adenocarcinoma was predominant (79.7%). *H. pylori* was detected in 19 patients (27.5%) and absent in 50 (72.5%). No significant associations were found between *H. pylori* status and age, sex, comorbidity, histological subtype, tumor location, or intestinal metaplasia ($p > 0.05$). Median OS was 18 months in *H. pylori*-negative patients and 13 months in *H. pylori*-positive patients, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.298$). In this cohort, the presence of *H. pylori* did not independently influence clinicopathological features or overall survival, supporting existing evidence that its prognostic value remains limited. Nevertheless, eradication therapy continues to be strongly endorsed for gastric cancer prevention, emphasizing its importance in population-level cancer control strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Gastric adenocarcinoma is one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality and morbidity worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, gastric cancer ranks fifth in incidence and fourth in cancer-related deaths, globally¹. Its etiology is multifactorial, involving genetic predisposition, environmental influences, dietary habits, and lifestyle factors. However, *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection is recognized as the most significant risk factor².

H. pylori is a spiral-shaped gram-negative bacterium first identified by Warren and Marshall³. By inducing chronic inflammation in the gastric mucosa, this bacterium was soon associated with the development of peptic ulcer disease and gastric cancer. *H. pylori* as a Group 1 carcinogen, underscoring its pivotal role in gastric carcinogenesis⁴.

The process by which *H. pylori* infection leads to gastric adenocarcinoma is described as the "Correa cascade." This sequence begins with chronic gastritis, progressing to atrophic gastritis, intestinal metaplasia, dysplasia, and ultimately, adenocarcinoma. Cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA) and vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA) are particularly important. CagA-positive strains enter epithelial cells, promoting cellular proliferation and genetic instability, whereas VacA suppresses immune responses and modulates the tumor microenvironment⁵⁻⁷. These mechanisms, combined with chronic inflammation and generation of reactive oxygen species, facilitate DNA damage and contribute to malignant transformation⁸.

Epidemiological evidence has demonstrated that *H. pylori* infection significantly increases the risk of gastric cancer. In contrast, the relationship appears weaker in cardia adenocarcinomas, in which factors such as gastroesophageal reflux disease and obesity play more prominent roles⁹.

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In recent years, randomized controlled trials have demonstrated that *H. pylori* eradication reduces the incidence of gastric cancer¹⁰. However, the effectiveness of eradication varies depending on the duration of infection, host genetic characteristics, and the histopathological stage at the time of treatment. In particular, its protective effect is limited in patients who have already developed intestinal metaplasia or dysplasia¹¹. Furthermore, antibiotic resistance and concerns regarding cost-effectiveness continue to challenge the feasibility of widespread eradication strategies at the public health level¹².

A better understanding of the relationship between *H. pylori* infection and gastric adenocarcinoma is of critical importance for both clinical management and preventive strategies. Current research is focused on the development of vaccines targeting bacterial virulence factors, the use of host genetic polymorphisms for risk stratification, and the identification of novel biomarkers¹³⁻¹⁵.

In this retrospective study, the association between *H. pylori* infection and clinicopathological features of gastric adenocarcinomas was investigated. *H. pylori* plays a pivotal role in gastric carcinogenesis through mechanisms involving chronic inflammation, atrophic gastritis, and intestinal metaplasia. Accordingly, we evaluated the potential relationship between the presence of *H. pylori* and the different histopathological subtypes of gastric adenocarcinoma.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This retrospective study included 69 patients diagnosed with gastric adenocarcinoma who underwent diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up at Sivas Cumhuriyet University Faculty of Medicine Research and Training Hospital between January 1, 2023, and December 1, 2024. The demographic and clinical data of all patients were obtained from hospital records and electronic databases. Information on patient age, sex, smoking status, and alcohol consumption history was recorded. In addition, overall survival status was assessed during clinical follow-up.

Histopathological evaluation included detailed documentation of tumor localization, histological grade, histological subtype, and presence of intestinal metaplasia. All samples were examined using routine hematoxylin-eosin staining, and the

presence of *H. pylori* was investigated by histochemical Giemsa staining. The slides were independently evaluated by four pathologists, and discrepancies were resolved by consensus.

Ethical Approval

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Sivas Cumhuriyet University, Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Board (Date: 16.01.2025; Decision No: 2025-01/70).

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 27.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The normality of distribution for continuous variables was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov and Shapiro–Wilk tests. Normally distributed numerical variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while non-normally distributed data were presented as median (min–max). The relationship between *Helicobacter pylori* status and clinicopathological parameters was evaluated using the Chi-Square test. Overall survival (OS) was estimated by the Kaplan–Meier method, and comparisons between study groups were performed with the log-rank test. Survival time was calculated from the date of diagnosis to either death or last follow-up. Patients who were alive at the last follow-up were censored at that date. Cases with missing key outcome data were excluded from the relevant analyses, and no imputation methods were applied. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 69 patients were included in this study. Of these, 31 (44.9%) were aged ≤ 65 years and 38 (55.1%) were aged > 65 years. The cohort comprised 49 males (71.0%) and 20 females (29.0%). Comorbidities were present in 34 patients (49.3%) and absent in 35 (50.7%). Regarding smoking status, 30 patients (43.5%) were non-smokers, 25 (36.2%) were smokers, and 14 (20.3%) had an unknown status. Alcohol consumption was reported in 22 patients (31.9%), absent in 23 patients (33.3%), and unknown in 24 patients (34.8%). Histologically, 55 cases (79.7%) were of the intestinal type, and 14 (20.3%) were of the diffuse type. Tumor localization was most common in the corpus-antrum (46; 66.7%), followed by the

cardia (21; 30.4%), and pylorus (2; 2.9%). Intestinal although the difference was not statistically significant metaplasia was detected in 48 patients (69.6%) and was (p=0.179, Table 1). absent in 21 patients (30.4%). During follow-up, 43 patients (62.3%) died, whereas 26 (37.7%) survived.

In this study, 50 patients who tested negative for *H. pylori* were compared with 19 patients who tested positive (Figure 1). Regarding age distribution, 25 patients (50.0%) in the negative group and 6 patients (31.6%) in the positive group were ≤65 years old, whereas 25 (50.0%) and 13 (68.4%) were >65 years old, respectively (p=0.135). Male sex was observed in 34 patients (68.0%) in the negative group and 15 patients (78.9%) in the positive group (p=0.280). Comorbidities were present in 23 (46.0%) and 11 (57.9%) patients in the negative and positive groups, respectively (P =0.270). Non-smokers constituted 25 (50.0%) in the negative group and five (26.3%) in the positive group, approaching statistical significance (p=0.058). Alcohol consumption was not significantly different between groups (p=0.929). The histological subtype, tumor localization, and intestinal metaplasia did not differ significantly (p>0.05). Mortality was higher in the positive group (14, 73.7%) than in the negative group (29, 58.0%),

Figure 1 (A) Histopathological image showing intestinal-type adenocarcinoma with glandular differentiation.(B) Histopathological image demonstrating signet-ring cell carcinoma characterized by abundant intracytoplasmic mucin displacing the nucleus (H&Ex200). (C,D) Histochemical Giemsa staining confirming *Helicobacter pylori* positivity within the gastric mucosa (Giemsa x200).

Variables		Total n(%)	<i>H.pylori</i> negative n (%)	<i>H.pylori</i> positive n (%)	P
Age	≤65	31 (44.9)	25 (50.0)	6 (31.6)	0.135
	>65	38 (55.1)	25 (50.0)	13 (68.4)	
Sex	Male	49 (71.0)	34 (68.0)	15 (78.9)	0.280
	Female	20 (29.0)	16 (32.0)	4 (21.1)	
Comorbidity	No	35 (50.7)	27 (54.0)	8 (42.1)	0.270
	Yes	34 (49.3)	23 (46.0)	11 (57.9)	
Smoking	No	30 (43.5)	25 (50.0)	5 (26.3)	0.058
	Yes	25 (36.2)	17 (34.0)	8 (42.1)	
	Unknown	14 (20.3)	8 (16.0)	6 (31.6)	
Alcohol consumption	No	23 (33.3)	17 (34.0)	6 (31.6)	0.929
	Yes	22 (31.9)	15 (30.0)	7 (36.8)	
	Unknown	24 (34.8)	18 (36.0)	6 (31.6)	
Histological type	Intestinal	55 (79.7)	40 (80.0)	15 (78.9)	0.582
	Diffuse	14 (20.3)	10 (20.0)	4 (21.1)	
Tumor location	Cardia	21 (30.4)	15 (30.0)	6 (31.6)	0.685
	Corpus-Antrum	46 (66.7)	33 (66.0)	13 (68.4)	
	Pylorus	2 (2.9)	2 (4.0)	0 (0.0)	
Intestinal metaplasia	No	21 (30.4)	16 (32.0)	5 (26.3)	0.441
	Yes	48 (69.6)	34 (68.0)	14 (73.7)	
Survival status	No	26 (37.7)	21 (42.0)	5 (26.3)	0.179
	Yes	43 (62.3)	29 (58.0)	14 (73.7)	

Table 1. Relationship between *H. pylori* status and clinicopathological variables in patients with gastric adenocarcinoma

Forty-three patients (62.3%) died during the median follow-up of 36 months. The median overall survival (OS) was 18 months (95% CI: 14.142–22.118). In *H. pylori*-negative patients, the median OS was estimated to be 18 months (95% CI: 9.96–27.23). In contrast, *H. pylori*-positive patients had a median OS of 13 months (95% CI, 4.170–22.370). The difference observed between the *H. pylori*-negative and *H. pylori*-positive groups was not statistically significant ($p = 0.298$).

Figure 2. Kaplan–Meier survival curves demonstrating overall survival according to *Helicobacter pylori* status.

DISCUSSION

Although the pivotal role of *H. pylori* in the pathogenesis of gastric adenocarcinoma is well established, its impact on prognosis after tumor development remains controversial. In our retrospective cohort, the median OS was shorter in *H. pylori*-positive patients than in *H. pylori*-negative patients; however, this difference was not statistically significant. These findings are consistent with much of the literature, suggesting that *H. pylori* status may not be an independent prognostic marker. For example, a recent post-gastrectomy cohort study reported that *H. pylori* infection did not significantly affect overall survival, although subgroup analyses suggested potential variability in specific patient populations¹⁶.

A meta-analysis published in 2022 reported that gastric cancer patients with *H. pylori* positivity demonstrated improved survival outcomes and recommended closer surveillance for those who were *H. pylori*-negative at diagnosis. These observations partially align with the hypothesis that bacteria may modulate immune responses within the tumor microenvironment. However, methodological heterogeneity across studies and variability in effect size substantially limit the generalizability of these findings¹⁷.

However, evidence for *Helicobacter pylori* eradication as a **primary preventive strategy** against gastric cancer is considerably more robust. *H. pylori* eradication following endoscopic resection of early gastric neoplasia halved the incidence of metachronous gastric cancer compared with placebo. These results underscore that eradication is a highly effective public health intervention. Therefore, consensus guidelines, most notably from the Maastricht VI/Florence groups, strongly endorse testing and treatment of *H. pylori* infection to reduce gastric cancer risk, particularly when conducted before the onset of atrophic gastritis or intestinal metaplasia^{18–20}.

Nevertheless, the practical implementation of eradication strategies must overcome several challenges, including rising rates of antibiotic resistance, regional variations in treatment efficacy, and concerns regarding cost-effectiveness. Consequently, guidelines advocate tailored approaches that incorporate regional epidemiology, antibiotic susceptibility testing, and optimal first-line or rescue regimens to ensure and minimize successful eradication²¹.

In our dataset, *H. pylori* status was not significantly associated with age, sex, comorbidity, histological type (intestinal vs.

diffuse), tumor location (cardia vs. corpus-antrum vs. pylorus), or the presence of intestinal metaplasia. This finding supports the interpretation that once gastric carcinoma has developed, the presence of the bacterium may no longer serve as a dominant factor influencing tumor phenotype or stage. Similarly, mortality was higher among *H. pylori*-positive patients, but the difference was not statistically significant. This may reflect limitations, such as sample size and treatment heterogeneity, which likely reduced the statistical power. Recent large cohort studies have suggested that *H. pylori* eradication could improve survival in patients with infected gastric cancer; however, establishing causality requires prospective studies controlling for potential confounders, including disease stage, surgical resection status, and treatment modalities²².

The main limitations of our study include its retrospective design, reliance on histochemical methods (Giemsa staining) for the detection of *Helicobacter pylori*, and heterogeneity in treatment strategies. One of the main limitations of our study is the relatively small sample size, which inevitably restricts the statistical power of subgroup analyses; this factor should be considered when interpreting the results. Future research should focus on prospective designs that integrate molecular bacterial markers and tumor microenvironment characteristics while also testing their interactions with therapeutic interventions. Such an approach could help clarify whether *H. pylori* has predictive, if not strictly prognostic, value, particularly in relation to eradication therapy or response to immunotherapy, and may ultimately pave the way for personalized strategies in selected patient subgroups.

In conclusion, in our cohort the presence of *H. pylori* did not emerge as an independent factor influencing overall survival, aligning with the “neutral” evidence reported across the heterogeneous literature. Nonetheless, the strong body of evidence supporting the preventive value of eradication therapy underscores the continued importance of combating *H. pylori* infection at the population level as an effective cancer prevention strategy.

Conflicts of Interest Statement: The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

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